

CONSTITUTION OF HALOGENATED RESACETO AND PROPIOPHENONES.

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4-Chlororesorcin when heated with acetic acid and propionic acid, yields 5-chlororesacetophenone and 5-chlororespropiophenone respectively. Similarly 4-bromoresorcin yields with acetic acid 5-bromoresacetophenone. The constitution of these halogenated ketones has been determined and it has been found that they do not condense with acetoacetic ester to form coumarins.

The work described in this paper, is the outcome of the investigations carried to establish the constitution of the coumarins obtained by Agarwal and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 109) by the condensation of resacetophenone with acetoacetic ester and its alkyl derivatives. It may be noted in passing that the coumarin, described by Agarwal and Dutt (*loc. cit.*), is not a coumarin at all but pure resacetophenone and it is not possible to effect the condensation of resacetophenone with acetoacetic ester under the experimental conditions of the authors (*cf.* Chakravarti and Chakravarty, *Science and Culture*, 1937, **3**, 244; Sethna, Shah and Shah, *Current Science*, 1937, **6**, 93; Limaye, *Rasayanam*, 1, 101).

Halogenated resaceto- and propiophenones have been prepared from the corresponding halogenated resorcins by Nencki's reaction. 4-Chlororesorcin and 4-bromoresorcin (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 791; Chakravarti and Mukerjee, *ibid.*, 1938, **15**, 493) have been found to yield halogenated ketones readily, which might have the alternative structures (I) or (II). In order to decide between the two structures the halogenated ketones have been reduced by Clemmensen's method and the halogenated *C*-alkyl-resorcins, thus obtained, have been condensed with acetoacetic ester producing coumarins. If the halogenated ketones possess the structure (I) it would produce a 5-hydroxycoumarin (III or IIIa) but if it has the constitution (II) it would lead to a 7-hydroxycoumarin (IV). It has been found that chloroethylresorcin and chloropropylresorcin, the Clemmensen reduction products of chlororesacetophenone and chlororespropiophenone respectively, condense with acetoacetic ester or its alkyl derivatives forming compounds, which give intense yellow colour and do not show blue-violet fluorescence in alkaline solution characteristic of 7-hydroxycoumarins. Hence chlororesaceto- and propiophenones are respectively 5-chlororesacetophenone (I, R=Cl; R'=H) and 5-chlororespro-

piophenone (I, R=Cl ; R'=Me). The preparation of the identical chlororesacetophenone by the chlorination of 4-ethylresorcin with sulphuryl chloride confirms the above constitution.

It should be observed that during the reduction of 5-chlororespropio-phenone by Clemmensen's method, along with chloropropylresorcin a halogen-free reduction product has been isolated which has been identified as 4-propylresorcin, since it produces a coumarin by condensation with acetoacetic ester, which is identical in all respects with 7-hydroxy-6-propyl-4-methylcoumarin, obtained from an authentic sample of 4-propylresorcin prepared by Clemmensen's reduction of respropiofenone.

The removal of halogen atom in Clemmensen's reduction is found not to be unusual as in the case of bromoresacetophenone, the ketone derived from 4-bromoresorcin, a non-halogenated product has been obtained quantitatively. The latter has been identified to be 4-ethylresorcin, since it produces 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-ethylcoumarin, identical with the coumarin derived from an authentic sample of 4-ethylresorcin by condensation with acetoacetic ester. The isolation of 4-ethylresorcin from bromoresacetophenone proves definitely that the latter has the constitution (I, R=Br, R'=H).

It has been found during this investigation that the halogenated resaceto- and propiophenones do not condense with acetoacetic ester in the presence of condensing agents such as alcoholic sodium ethoxide, syrupy phosphoric acid, dry hydrochloric acid, piperidine and anhydrous aluminium chloride, the unchanged halogenated ketones being recovered in each case.

The study of the ketones from the halogenated resorcins led us to prepare the ketones from 4-chloroorcin (Chakravarti and Mukerjee, *loc. cit.*) and to elucidate their constitution in an analogous manner, but the results obtained are perplexing. 4-Chloroorcin, when condensed with benzyl cyanide according to Hoesch's method, yields instead of a halogenated ketone a substance, which does not contain chlorine and which is not identical with the ketone obtained from orcin and benzyl cyanide. The two substances differ widely and further the Clemmensen's reduction products are also different. The ketone from chloroorcin and benzyl cyanide (needles) melts at 140° . It gives violet colour with ferric chloride and on Clemmensen's reduction gives a substance, m. p. 127° . The ketone from orcin and benzyl cyanide (long flat prisms) melts at 160° . It does not give any colour with ferric chloride and the Clemmensen's reduction product melts at 72° , turning brown rapidly in air.

In the course of this investigation it was thought advisable to find out how the pyrone ring was affected under Clemmensen's condition. Coumarin itself, on Clemmensen's reduction, yields a crystalline substance (m.p. 235°). (Found: C, 72.83, 73.01; H, 4.67, 4.81; M.W. by Rast's method, 272). It has not been possible to assign any constitution to the reduction product but it may be a product of pinacoline type.

EXPERIMENTAL.

*5-Chlororesacetophenone.—4-Chlororesorcinn (25 g.) was added to a solution of freshly fused zinc chloride (25 g.) in glacial acetic acid (25 c. c.) and the mixture heated to 145° for 3 minutes. The cold red syrupy mass was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 c. c.) and water (25 c. c.), when chlororesacetophenone separated as a yellow crystalline mass. It was collected and crystallised from hot water as needles, m.p. 171° , yield 10 g. It gives a violet colour with ferric chloride. It is readily soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform and acetic acid. (Found: Cl, 18.94. $C_8H_7O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 19.03 per cent).

The semicarbazone, prepared in the usual way, melts at 315° . (Found: N, 17.80. $C_8H_{10}O_3N_3Cl$ requires N, 17.25 per cent).

4-Chloro-6-ethylresorcin.—5-Chlororesacetophenone (5 g.), zinc amalgam (40 g.) and hydrochloric acid (1: 2, 120 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours with the addition of a fresh quantity of hydrochloric acid during the reduction. The greenish yellow solution was filtered and the filtrate after being saturated with common salt was extracted with ether, the ether evaporated, when an oil was obtained which on cooling and keeping in vacuum solidified to a mass of crystals. It crystallised from a small quantity of water as needles, m.p. 84°, yield 3 g (Found: Cl, 20.69. $C_8H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 20.5 per cent).

6 (or 8)-Chloro-5-hydroxy-4-methyl-8 (or 6)-ethylcoumarin.—4-Chloro-6-ethylresorcin (1 g.) and acetoacetic ester (1 g) were condensed in the presence of sulphuric acid (2 c.c.) in the cold. The solution was kept overnight and poured into crushed ice and the crystalline product was recrystallised from rectified spirit as colourless prisms, m.p. 175°. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with intense yellow colour and does not show any fluorescence characteristic of 7-hydroxycoumarins. (Found: Cl, 14.61. $C_{12}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.8 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual way by heating with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in silky needles, m.p. 100°. (Found: Cl, 12.55. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 12.65 per cent).

The identical coumarin (m.p. and mixed m.p. 175°) was obtained by heating 4-chloro-6-ethylresorcin (2 g.), acetoacetic ester (2 g.) and phosphorus pentoxide (10 g.) on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour (Simonis' reaction). The reaction mixture was treated with powdered ice and the oil separating was extracted with ether. On removing ether the oil was dissolved with 10% alkali and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid. The process was repeated several times when the oil solidified on chilling. It crystallised from alcohol (charcoal).

6 (or 8)-Chloro-5-hydroxy-3 : 4-dimethyl-8 (or 6)-ethylcoumarin was obtained by condensing 4-chloro-6-ethylresorcin with α -methylacetoacetic ester in presence of sulphuric acid in the usual manner. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 183°. It dissolves in alkali with a yellow colouration. (Found: Cl, 13.91. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.05 per cent).

Formation of 4-Chloro-6-ethylresorcin by the Action of Sulphuryl Chloride on 4-Ethylresorcin.—Sulphuryl chloride (5 g.) was added drop by drop to ice-cooled ethereal solution of 4-ethylresorcin, obtained by the reduction of resacetophenone, when there was a copious evolution of hydrochloric acid and sulphur dioxide. The ethereal

solution was washed by sodium bicarbonate solution and then by water and the ether allowed to evaporate, when an oil was obtained which solidified on keeping and stirring. After removing the adhering tar on a porous plate it was crystallised from hot water (charcoal), m.p. 85°, yield 1 g. It is identical in all respects with 4-chloro-6-ethylresorcin, prepared above, and forms identical coumarin on condensation with acetoacetic ester.

5-Chlororespropiofenone.—Chlororesorcin (25 g.) and a solution of freshly fused zinc chloride (25 g.) in propionic acid (25 g.) was boiled for 3 minutes. The red syrupy liquid on cooling was treated with powdered ice and hydrochloric acid, when an oil separated which solidified on chilling. It crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) as yellow needles, m.p. 90°, yield 10 g. It gives a violet colour with ferric chloride and is soluble in boiling water. (Found: Cl, 17.29. $C_9H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 17.70 per cent).

Clemmensen's Reduction of 5-Chlororespropiofenone: Formation of 4-Chloro-6-propylresorcin and 4-Propylresorcin.—5-Chlororespropiofenone (5 g.), zinc amalgam (20 g.), hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) and water (60 c.c.) were refluxed for 5 hours. The yellow solution was filtered hot, when crystals separated on cooling. It was crystallised from luke warm water as colourless needles, m.p. 63°, yield 3 g. It gives a blue colour with ferric chloride. (Found: Cl, 18.79. $C_9H_{11}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 19.03 per cent).

The mother-liquor after the separation of 4-chloro-6-propylresorcin was saturated with common salt and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract dehydrated by calcium chloride and ether evaporated. The oil separating solidified on scratching. It does not contain chlorine and is found to be identical with propylresorcin, prepared by the reduction of respropiofenone (*vide infra*).

Clemmensen's Reduction of Respropiofenone.—Respropiofenone (5 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.), water (40 c.c.), zinc amalgam (20 g.), alcohol (10 c.c.) were refluxed for 5 hours. The filtered solution was saturated with common salt, extracted with ether, ethereal extract was dehydrated and ether evaporated, when an oil was obtained which solidified on chilling. It crystallised in colourless needles from petroleum ether (b.p. 50°), m.p. 77°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 70.78; H, 7.8. $C_9H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 71.05; H, 7.89 per cent).

Condensation of Propylresorcin with Ethyl Acetoacetate: Formation of 6-Propyl-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin.—6-Propylresorcin, obtained by the reduction of respropiofenone or 5-chlororespropiofenone, was

condensed with ethyl acetoacetate using sulphuric acid in the usual manner. The product crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 174°. (Found : C, 71.48 ; H, 6.29. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.55 ; H, 6.42 per cent).

6-(or 8)-Chloro-5-hydroxy-4-methyl-8 (or 6)-propylcoumarin, the condensation product of 5-chlororesorpiophenone and ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of sulphuric acid, crystallised from alcohol as prisms, m.p. 185°. It is soluble in alkalis with intense yellow colour and does not show any blue-violet fluorescence characteristic of 7-hydroxycoumarins. (Found : Cl, 14.22. $C_{13}H_{13}O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.05 per cent).

* *5-Bromoresacetophenone*.—Bromoresorcin (5 g.) and a solution of fused zinc chloride (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 g.) were boiled for 3 minutes. The cold syrupy mass was treated with water acidulated with hydrochloric acid, when bromoresacetophenone separated. It was collected and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 167°. (Found : Br, 34.36. $C_8H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 34.63 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 255°. (Found: N, 14.96. $C_8H_{10}O_3N_3Br$ requires N, 14.59 per cent).

Clemmensen's Reduction of 5-Bromoresacetophenone: Formation of 4-Ethylresorcin.—5-Bromoresacetophenone (2 g.), zinc amalgam (20 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and water (40 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours. The solution was filtered and concentrated to half its volume and saturated with common salt and extracted with ether. On evaporation of ether an oil was obtained, which solidified on scratching. It crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 97°. It has been identified as 4-ethylresorcin as it does not depress the m.p. of 4-ethylresorcin obtained by reduction of resacetophenone and also forms the identical coumarin by its condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of sulphuric acid.

7-Hydroxy-6-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin.—The condensation product of 4-ethylresorcin and ethyl acetoacetate using sulphuric acid in the usual manner crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as needles, m.p. 210°. (Found : C, 70.86 ; H, 5.71. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.60 ; H, 5.8 per cent).

The Ketone obtained by Hoesch's Reaction of 4-Chloroorscin with Benzyl Cyanide and its Clemmensen's Reduction Product.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed into a dry ethereal solution of chloroorscin (10 g.) and benzyl cyanide (7.5 g.) containing fused zinc chloride (4 g.) and the solution cooled in ice. The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 days and the syrupy mass extracted with ether and the aqueous layer heated on a water-bath, when a brown oil separated, which was dissolved in ether. The ether was distilled off, when the oil solidified on standing for several days.

It was washed by sodium bicarbonate solution and then crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 140° , yield 3 g. It does not contain chlorine. It is soluble in boiling water and is moderately soluble in alcohol. It is soluble in alkalis and gives a violet colour with ferric chloride. (Found : C, 74.18; H, 5.7. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 5.7 per cent).

The above ketone (3 g.), hydrochloric acid (1:2, 60 c.c.), and zinc amalgam (20 g.) were refluxed for 8 hours. The melted product separating was separated and crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 127° , yield 1 g. It gives no colour with ferric chloride. It is soluble in alkalis forming a colourless solution. (Found : C, 77.1; H, 6.3 per cent).

The Ketone obtained by Hoesch's Reaction of Orcin with Benzyl Cyanide and its Clemmensen's Reduction Product—Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed into a cold ethereal solution of orcin (10 g.) and benzyl cyanide (10 g.) containing fused zinc chloride (4 g.) and the mixture was set aside for 2 days. The syrupy mass was shaken with ether, when the imino-hydrochloride separated. It was collected and heated with water on the water-bath, when the ketone separated as flat prisms, m.p. 160° , yield 5 g. It crystallises from dilute alcohol. It is soluble in alkalis and does not give any colour with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 72.98; H, 5.78 per cent).

The ketone (2 g.), zinc amalgam (20 g.) and hydrochloric acid (1:2, 60 c.c.) were refluxed for 8 hours. The solution was filtered hot and on cooling crystals separated. These were collected and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 72° , yield 1.5 g. It turns brown on exposure to air. It does not give any colour with ferric chloride and does not undergo Pechmann's reaction. (Found: C, 79.58; H, 7.44 per cent).

Reduction of Coumarin by Clemmensen's Method.—Coumarin (5 g.), zinc amalgam (20 g.), hydrochloric acid (1:2, 60 c.c.) were refluxed for 4 hours with the addition of 60 c.c. more of hydrochloric acid (1:2) gradually during the reduction. The cold solution was filtered and the solid on the filter paper was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 235° , yield 2 g. of the pure product. It is insoluble in alkali and does not decolourise bromine. [Found : C, 72.83, 73.01; H, 4.67, 4.81; M.W., (Rast's method), 272].

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